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A stylized logo for 'freewheel' rendered in a light blue, rounded, sans-serif font. The letters are interconnected, with the 'f' and 'e' on the left side being particularly prominent and overlapping.

PROGRESS REPORT M6

DELIVERABLE NUMBER D1

IRIS SRL

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports briefly on the overall progress of project FreeWheel at month 6, specifying also technical, administrative and financial progress.

Overall progress

The project started October the 1st, 2017. Alongside the “Project Management” workpackage (WP1), WP2 “Human centred requirements and objectives” started also as planned. In addition, some activities started also for WP3 “FreeWheel product design” – initially planned to start in month 6 – to provide direct feedback to WP2 and to exploit at best the co-creation opportunities given by WP2’s direct contact with end users. Some communication activities were also undertaken to exploit a sponsorship opportunity local to the Turin demosite community.

Technical progress

The active workpackages during the first semester, alongside WP1, were WP2, WP3 and WP9. WP2 focalised on the identification of the typical behaviours of users in terms of needs and expectations with respect to a mobility solution such as FreeWheel. WP3 identified main wheelchair manoeuvring issues and reviewed existing solutions of small size autonomous moving platforms, to identify architectures that could be built upon for the FreeWheel module.

Administrative progress

A remote kick off meeting (KOM) was held during the first month (Milestone 1), with a General Assembly held at IRIS’s premises in Turin in November 2017. Milestone 1 also included information on project policy, which was communicated during the KOM and supported by templates uploaded on a shared Google drive.

Deliverables expected in the first semester of the project were uploaded in draft form by the deadline set, finalized and submitted shortly after.

Some communication activities were undertaken with the sponsorship of a car adapted to the transport of disabled people in the same municipality of demosite 1.

Financial progress

Project spent at month 6 is an overall 9% of the budgeted expenditure. This is slightly lower than expected: however, this does not raise major concerns considering the make up of the project, as only WP2 and a small part of WP3 have been activated and significant expenditure in goods and services was not planned.

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Introduction

This document reports on overall progress of project FreeWheel, covering the first six months of the project and analysing in details technical, administrative and financial progress.

The project started October the 1st, 2017. Alongside the “Project Management” workpackage (WP1), WP2 “Human centred requirements and objectives” started also as planned. In addition, some activities started also for WP3 “FreeWheel product design” – initially planned to start in month 6 – to provide direct feedback to WP2 and to exploit at best the co-creation opportunities given by WP2’s direct contact with end users. Some communication activities were also undertaken to exploit a sponsorship opportunity local to the Turin demosite community.

The work is progressing well for the active workpackages thanks to the very collaborative approach of all partners. Furthermore, the presence of an end user of the service proposed by FreeWheel is a strong asset: this allows to implement a collaborative, co-creative approach to the design of the solution which sets the basis for an outcome of real community impact.

Technical Progress

Workpackage WP2: Human centred requirements and objectives

The main objective of this WP is to identify the design and functional requirements for FreeWheel integrated solution. The first task completed at the end of January with the definition of the archetype profiles, i.e. behavioural perspectives of users and prospect clients, which help to define FreeWheel main value propositions. These archetypes were depicted through interviewing of potential users and consultation with the partner representing the stakeholders most interested by the solution, i.e. people with permanent motor disabilities. This first step sets up the co-creative approach of the design of FreeWheel solution. The second task resulted in two experience maps representing the steps taken by the users of the solution from start to finish in the two selected settings, i.e. an indoor shopping mall and an outdoor tourist destination (e.g. archaeological site). The maps provide also the users perspective, more focused on the use of the service, providing information on the expected interactions and the overall interactions with the solution.

Workpackage WP3: FreeWheel product design

The main objective of this WP focuses on the design of the FreeWheel mobility mechatronic solution consisting of the active module (the motor), the connector with the wheel chair and the motion system (the wheels and support structure). Activities on this WP started earlier than planned to exploit the consultation opportunities provided by WP2. Some different models of wheelchairs were analysed, and some specific challenges of the users were gathered (e.g.: small front wheels are particularly difficult to manoeuvre especially on uneven pavement or with small steps or gaps): these are important elements to be included in the design of the module. This information also provided interesting insights for the review of existing four-wheels autonomous drive solutions that could be used as platforms or exemplars for the module.

Administrative Progress

A remote kick off meeting (KOM) was held October the 10th (Milestone 1), with a General Assembly held at IRIS’s premises in Turin on November 21st and 22nd 2017, with all beneficiaries represented in both cases.

Milestone 1 also included information on project policy, which was communicated during the KOM and supported by templates uploaded on a shared Google drive.

Deliverables expected in the first semester of the project were uploaded in draft form by the deadline set, finalized and submitted shortly after.

No new critical risks have arisen so far.

A sponsorship opportunity for a car adapted for the transport of disabled arose in December 2017: the coordinator destined some of the project's communication budget available for this initiative. The car, which is used in the Municipality of the demosite¹, carries the FreeWheel logo and a QR code to the website, which is to be published in April 2018.

Financial Progress

Project spent at month 6 is an overall 9% of the budgeted expenditure. This is slightly lower than expected: however, this does not raise major concerns considering the make up of the project, as only WP2 and a small part of WP3 have been activated and goods and services are still to be acquired.

Looking in details, for WP1 personnel time spent amounts to 10% of the total, with the Coordinator concentrating the most of the effort; for other members of the consortium, only participation to the 1st general assembly and filing of an internal financial monitoring sheet have been undertaken as project management activities. In preparation of deliverable D4 "Financial administrative report" due M12 and with the second General Assembly, the activities will pick up.

For WP2, the effort spent amounts to 41% of budget, which is in line with a low level activity for a project at start. However, WP2 is concluding in the next semester and the level of activity already planned will saturate the budgeted effort. Moreover, the contribution in terms of stakeholder experience and behaviours from partner Genny Angels is higher than expected. This positive effect is resulting in a lower impact on personnel resources during the research activities in WP2. At the same time, the high level of discoveries gathered during the research phase in WP2 is likely to require more effort in WP4. There is therefore an opportunity for moving some of the personnel budget from "WP2: Human centred requirements and objectives" to "WP4: Free Wheel service and digital touchpoints design" for the partner Keen Bull Sagl (leading both of the WPs). Specific details about the amount of budget will be defined during before the end of WP2.

The start of activities for WP3 equates to a 17% of budget spent; similarly, communication activities started early equates to 2% of budgeted effort.

Some 11% of "Other costs" were also spent, covering mainly travels and subsistence for the 1st General Assembly and the communication activities undertaken by IRIS.

Conclusions

Project FreeWheel is progressing overall in line with expectations. Deliverables are being submitted with very short delays and no further critical risks have arisen so far. The slight lower spent for WP2 is soon to be redressed as activities for the workpackage are already planned to pick up.

In the next six months, WP2 is reaching conclusion while activities on WP3 are ramping up. Communication and dissemination activities are also starting with the publication of the website first, then a scope-out of the dissemination opportunities.

The second GA is being held in Patras on May the 2nd and 3rd; in this occasion, the second proposed demosite will be visited to understand opportunities and challenges for the demonstration activities.

The progress report for month 12 will be delivered as Annual review report (D7) and a Financial Administrative report (D4).